

Research

Prediction of overall survival (OS) prognosis for chromophobe renal cell carcinoma of post nephrectomy patients: A SEER database study

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Abstract: The aim of this study based on the Overall Survival prognosis of patients with Chromophobe Renal Cell Carcinoma (ChRCC) is to help Urology department doctors to improve their clinical approach on ChRCC by giving out a clear idea on the choice of treatment methods and prognosis of this particular cancer.

This study included 3108 patients diagnosed with ChRCC from the Surveillance, Epidemiology, and End Results (SEER) database between 2010 and 2015. We collected data from a single center in China. In total, we selected from the period of 1st January 2010 to 31st December 2021, 225 patients diagnosed with ChRCC by the pathology department after nephrectomy was performed.

Chromophobe Renal Cell Carcinoma was more found in younger and middle age patients (50.19% & 36.81% from SEER; 74.22% & 24% from china). Patients with bigger tumor size (>108mm) are more likely to have a worse OS rate (HR-1 = 0.229; P= 0.0194). American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC) TNM stages in our study showed that there was a worse survival rate interval in older patients with T3 or T4. The Cancer-Specific Survival rate in our research is over 98% since there are less than 2% patients with Sarcomatoid features or Regional positive lymph-nodes after nephrectomy.

Chromophobe Renal Cell Carcinoma presents a favorable Overall Survival (OS) prognosis. Our study shows that significantly fewer patients present sarcomatoid features, which justifies the fact that ChRCC has a better Cancer-Specific Survival rate. However, those presenting sarcomatoid features with/without positive lymph-node have a poor prognosis. Although total nephrectomy remains the gold standard of treatment, we encourage that more future research should be done to develop a better oncological therapeutic treatment for those with metastasis.

Keywords: Renal Cell Carcinoma; Overall Survival; Prognosis; Nephrectomy; Chromophobe Renal Cell Carcinoma; Surveillance, Epidemiology, and End Results (SEER)

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Accepted: 29 January, 2023; **Published:** 25 February, 2023

How to cite this article: Immacule Fiacre Megnisse Montcho (2023). Prediction of overall survival (OS) prognosis for chromophobe renal cell carcinoma of post nephrectomy patients: A SEER database study. *North American Academic Research*, 6(1), 249-258. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7675652>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

Renal Cell Carcinoma (RCC) is the most common tumor that attacks the kidneys (1). One of its subtypes is Chromophobe Renal Cell Carcinoma (ChRCC). It was first classified as a non-clear renal cell carcinoma and being described as a Chromophobe type by Theones et al. in 1985 (2). Nevertheless, it was only classified as a subtype of renal tumor a year later.

In recent studies, the American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC) TNM stages are one of the first systems to refer to when evaluating the Overall Survival prognosis in patients with ChRCC is concerned (3). Most patients with Chromophobe Renal Cell Carcinoma are diagnosed with T1 or T2 stage of disease (4). They are usually known to have a good post-surgery follow-up as well as a lower metastasis spreading or even recurrence rate.

As much as it is known for its better prognosis compared to the other subtypes of RCC, a small amount of ChRCC was associated with the possibility of spreading metastases and death, especially in those with complicated pathological features like sarcomatoid features and regional positive lymph-nodes found during or after the nephrectomy(5).

Although there have been some studies about the use of chemotherapy or radiotherapy, and the development of other methods such as oral inhibitor drugs, Surgical resection, either Radical Nephrectomy (RN) or Partial Nephrectomy (PN) remains the most viable choice of treatment of ChRCC(6).

We conducted a constructive analysis of the overall survival of ChRCC in this study to help with clinical approaches to this subtype of renal cancer.

Methods and Materials

During our research, with validation by the ethics committee of the first affiliated hospital of Zhengzhou University, we collected data from a single center in china. In total, we selected, from the period of 1st January 2010 to 31st December 2021, 225 patients diagnosed with ChRCC by the pathology department after nephrectomy was performed.

In quest of supporting our results, the Surveillance, Epidemiology, and End Results (SEER) 18-registries database was queried for all patients who were diagnosed with ChRCC between the years of 2010 and 2015 to be able to have a minimum follow-up of at least 3 to 5 years.

To be in possession of the detailed information needed, we downloaded SEER*Stat software version 8.3.8. We proceeded according to the International Classification of Diseases for Oncology 3rd edition (ICD-O-3), primary site codes C65.9 (kidney and renal pelvis), and histological/behavior codes 8271/3 (Renal cell carcinoma, Chromophobe type). The selection was based on the following criteria : (1) patients who underwent nephrectomy, (2) patients diagnosed at any age, (3) patients with active follow-up, patients histologically diagnosed with the first malignant tumor, (5) patients for whom the cause of death was available, (6) patients with known clinical data, (7)patients whose survival time was known and were at least one month and (8)ethical approval.

We collected in total 10583 patients' information. After filtering, we found 3108 patients in the SEER database who were suitable for our research. (SEER) 18-registries database, included variables such as age at diagnosis, race, sex, American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC) stage, histological grade, T stage, N stage, M stage, SEER stage, surgery method, chemotherapy, radiotherapy, tumor size, marital status, sarcomatoid features, regional positive lymph node and cause of death. We decided to regroup all the other cause of death, which is not renal and pelvis, together since our research purpose was mainly about the renal and pelvis.

We used the SAS 9.4 software for the patient demographic tables to get the HR confidence intervals tables 1,2&3. Statistical significance was set at $P \leq 0.05$. Vital status recode (study cutoff used) was used as an event variable, and dead was assigned a value of 1 as a positive event to explore the impact of other variables on vital status re-code (study

cutoff used) and Survival months. HR means that one of the classifications has a 1-HR (HR<1) or increased HR-1 (HR>1) relative to the survival risk of the reference, and the HR value is equal to 1, indicating that there is no effect on the occurrence of positive events.

Result

It is essential to report that our research is based on five years follow-up from SEER database and ten years follow-up from a Chinese single-center. . There were only 13.77% (n = 428) from the SEER database and 17.78% (n = 40) from the Chinese single-center population during that time period. After the demographic analysis of our patients shown in table1, we found that, either from the SEER database or Chinese single-center, our disease of research, ChRCC is more frequent in younger and middle age patients (50.19% & 36.81% from SEER; 74.22%& 24% from china).

The more voluminous the tumor size is, the less chance the patients have an overall survival (OS) rate with HR >1, (51-108mm,n=947; 30.47% HR-1=0.235; p=0.0001 and >108mm, n=351, 11.29% HR-1 = 0.229; P= 0.0194).

Despite the fact that there were more patients with smaller tumors (n = 1810; 58.24%), our study results show in Table 1 that patients who received total nephrectomy as treatment had a better OS rate (HR = 0.848; p = 0.0004).

Table1: Clinical and demographic features of chromophobe renal cell carcinoma patients after nephrectomy

Variables	SEER database n(%)	SEER data- base HR(95% con- fidence in- terval)	P value	Chinese data n(%)	Chinese data HR(95% confidence interval)	P value
Age						
<61	1560(50.19%)	Reference		167(74.22%)	Reference	
61-74	1144(36.81%)	0.018	0.6731	54(24%)	0.234	0.1739
>74	404(13%)	*0.084	0.2466	4(1.78%)	*0.442	0.5449
Race						
White	2505(80.6%)	Reference				
Black	370(11.9%)	*0.011	0.8845		NA	
Others	233(7.5%)	0.033	0.5991	225(100%)		
Sex						
Male	1706(54.89%)	Reference	0.1715	97(43.11%)	Reference	
Female	1402(45.11%)	*0.056		128(56.89%)	*0.022	0.8952
Tumor size(mm)						
<51	1810(58.24%)	Reference		132(58.67%)	Reference	
51-108	947(30.47%)	*0.235	0.0001	79(35.11%)	*0.181	0.3677
>108	351(11.29%)	*0.229	0.0194	11(4.89%)	*0.004	0.993
Missing				3(1.33%)	NA	
Surgery						
PN	1475(47.46%)	Reference		76(33.78%)	Reference	
RN	1633(52.54%)	0.848	0.0004	149(66.22%)	0.074	0.6934
Marital status						
Married	2393(76.99%)	Reference		225(100%)	NA	
Unmarried	518(16.67%)	*0.149	0.0096			

Unknown	197(6.34%)	0.007	0.9292
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PN: Partial Nephrectomy; RN: Radical Nephrectomy; Statistical significance was set at $P \leq 0.05$; *: HR-1

In table 2, we show the results of the pathological features in our study. With the grade results that are known from the pathology department of our single-center in china and the SEER database, it is seen that most patients were diagnosed with grade II of ChRCC (n=1042; 33.53% from SEER database and n=53; 23.56% from china). Surprisingly, we found out that more patients were diagnosed with grade III (n=636; 20.46% from SEER database and n=31; 13.78% from china) than grade I (n=165; 5.31% from SEER database and n=12; 5.33% from china). One thing to be noticed was that a significantly lower percentage of patients were diagnosed with grade IV (4.38% from SEER database and 2.57% from china). Overall analysis with grade I as the reference, patients diagnosed with grade II has better OS rate (HR=0.174; p=0.033) than grade III and IV, which also happened to have good HR values (HR<1), respectively HR = 0.152 and HR = 0.056. There were more patients (66.38%) with AJCC stage I. The rest of the patients were divided into the other AJCC stages, and the lower the stage was, the more percentage of patients it had. Also, with AJCC stage I as a reference, patients with AJCC IV have a worse OS rate HR>1 (HR-1=3.544) compared to others.

From our patients' information on the TNM system, there were higher percentages in more miniature stages, either T, N or M. Additionally, with T1 as a reference, neither patients with T2 nor T3 had better confidence intervals for OS.

Even though we have noted that the SEER stage "regional" did not affect the OS confidential interval (HR=1) of the patients who were diagnosed at that particular stage, there was more frequency in the localized stage and the lower presence in the SEER stage "distant".

Most patients did not present sarcomatoid features, and the same was noticed with regional positive lymph-nodes after nephrectomy. However, the ones who presented sarcomatoid features did not show a positive OS rate with HR>1.

Finally, less than 4% of patients' causes of death were related to the kidney and pelvis.

Table 2: Univariate and multivariate cox analysis of OS and CSS

Variables	SEER database n(%)	SEER data- base HR(95% confidence interval)	P val- ues	Chinese data n(%)	Chinese data HR(95% confidence interval)	P value
Grade						
Grade I	165(5.31%)	Reference		12(5.33%)	Reference	
Grade II	1042(33.53%)	0.174	0.033	53(23.56%)	*0.224	0.6086
Grade III	636(20.46%)	0.152	0.0882	31(13.78%)	0.472	0.1437
Grade IV	136(4.38%)	0.056	0.6695	6(2.67%)	*0.012	0.9842
Unknown	1129(36.33%)	*0.058	0.5366	123(54.67%)	0.428	0.1312
AJCC stage						
I	2063(66.38%)	Reference		152(67.56%)	Reference	
II	518(16.67%)	0.409	0.3679	38(16.89%)	*0.08	0.7256
III	462(14.86%)	0.413	0.3714	27(12%)	0.121	0.605
IV	40(1.29%)	*3.544	0.9996	3(1.33%)	0.22	0.6876
Unknown	25(0.8%)	*0.033	0.9445	5(2.22%)	0.73	0.0616

T stage						
T1	2100(67.57%)	Reference		112(49.78%)	Reference	
T2	534(17.18%)	*0.533	0.4644	90(40%)	*1.043	0.8101
T3	465(14.96%)	*0.722	0.3604	23(10.22%)	0.421	0.0892
T4	9(0.29%)	0.204	0.9999			
N stage						
N0	3040(97.81%)	Reference		216(96%)	Reference	
N1	37(1.19%)	*0.393	0.6391	2(0.89%)	0.777	0.1012
NX	31(1%)	0.794	0.5755	7(3.11%)	*0.323	0.6025
M stage						
M0	3076(98.97%)	Reference		225(100%)	NA	
M1	32(1.03%)	*0.144	1			
SEER stage						
Localized	2606(83.85%)	Reference		196(87.11%)	Reference	
Regional	469(15.09%)	1		26(11.56%)	*0.449	0.1464
Distant	33(1.06%)	0.224	0.9996	3(1.33%)	0.728	0.1383
Sarcomatoid features						
Absent	3066(98.65%)	Reference		225(100%)	NA	
Present	42(1.35%)	*0.203	0.4166			
RPLN						
Negative or non-existent	3077(99%)	Reference		221(98.22%)	Reference	
Positive	31(1%)	0.787	0.7369	4(1.78%)	0.441	0.3163
Cause of death						
Others				217(96.44%)	NA	0.978
Kidney and renal pelvis	3010(96.85%)	NA		8(3.56%)	NA	
	98(3.15%)	NA	0.8804			

RPLN: Regional Positive Lymph-Node; Statistical significance was set at $P \leq 0.05$; *: HR-1; American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC)

Table3: Estimation ratio of Overall Survival prognosis in Chromophobe Renal Cell Carcinoma

Superior Ratio estimation			
Event	Ratio	Lower ratio in 95% confidential interval	Upper ratio in 95% confidential interval
Grade group			
Grade I-Grade II	1.199	0.720	1.995
Grade I-Grade III	1.364	0.793	2.346
Grade I-Grade IV	1.701	0.734	3.946
Grade I-Unknown	1.962	1.164	3.309
AJCC stage group			
I-II	0.633	0.030	13.473
I-III	1.094	<0.001	>999.999

I-IV	0.225	<0.001	>999.999
I-Unknown	<0.001	<0.001	>999.999
T stage group			
T1-T2	1.751	0.082	37.343
T1-T3	0.729	0.065	8.146
T1-T4	1.828	<0.001	>999.999
N stage group			
N0-N1	0.386	0.014	10.434
N0-NX	>999.999	<0.001	>999.999
M_stage group			
M0-M1	0.905	<0.001	>999.999
Surgery group			
Partial nephrectomy-			
Total nephrectomy	0.487	0.366	0.647
Sarcomatoid features group			
Absent-Present	0.569	0.169	1.916
RPLN group			
Negative or none ex-			
istence-Positive	1.458	0.058	36.954
Cause of death			
others-Kidney and	<0.001	<0.001	>999.999
Renal Pelvis			

RPLN: Regional Positive Lymph-Node

Discussion

Chromophobe Renal Cell Carcinoma (ChRCC), despite being known as one of the most common types of RCC behind the others such as Clear Renal cell carcinoma, is still not that frequently found in China (7). In fact, most clinical articles about ChRCC have less than 200 patients from Chinese centers. Our research was based on 225 patients from a single center in china and also we had 3108 patients from the SEER database. The aim of this study based on the OS of patients with ChRCC is to help clinical urology department doctors to improve their approach on ChRCC by giving out a clear idea on the choice of treatment methods and prognosis of this particular cancer.

As it has been noted in many scientific research papers, most ChRCC patients find out they have a growing tumor on their kidneys by incidents during a physical checkup (8). In many cases, patients do not show symptoms. Even if some have symptoms, there are usually the common ones associated with the urinary system, such as: back pain, hematuria, urinary incontinence etc (9). It has been proven that ChRCC is usually seen like any other tumor on the kidney by a CT scan. It is confirmed by the pathology department after a nephrectomy or a biopsy is performed before the nephrectomy (10).

Most ChRCC cases have been reported in younger patients and in middle age patients, meaning the older the patient was, the worst prognostic they might have(11). Our study has joined that logic by proving with our results that either from the SEER database or our single center in China, more patients under 61years old were easier to diagnose with

ChRCC than older patients. But also, according to our results, older patients seemed to have the worst OS rate than younger patients with $HR > 1$.

Like other Renal Cell Carcinoma types, the tumor size can also affect the choice of surgery from, either a partial nephrectomy, or a total nephrectomy to treat ChRCC(12). Some studies have proven that the tumor size did not have an essential role in the prognosis of ChRCC. Therefore, some studies showed that patients with bigger tumor sizes did not have a favorable Overall Survival rate(13-14). Furthermore, our study had proven that patients with tumor size over 51mm had a worst Overall Survival rate ($HR > 1$ & $P < 0.05$). Although surgery perform, a choice of nephrectomy according to the expertise of the surgeon in the particular case. Our study proves that patients who received total nephrectomy had a better prognosis, and we are suggesting that surgeons may consider this result more in their future treatment. Since we knew from (Hoffmann et al., 2008) (15) that liver and lung are the main metastasis sites of this type of cancer, some studies have shown different oncological treatments to the advanced version of ChRCC. In addition, there were chemotherapy, radiation therapy and oral inhibitors that had been an object of research in the past (16). However, we were not able to include analyses about oncological treatment in our study due to lack of data and also SEER "terms and conditions" warned us about the fact that these treatments' data might have an incomplete assessment.

The clinico-pathological grading of ChRCC has been a veritable subject of research in recent years(17). Even if there is still a debate about it, it has been proven, and so did our study of research, that patients diagnosed with grade I & II were more favorable to better Overall Survival rate than the rest. Talking about the pathology of ChRCC would definitely require us to give an approach about the AJCC stages, the TMN system and other pathological features associated with ChRCC (18).

Firstly, it is crucial to notify that the AJCC TMN stage has been a fundamental key to predicting the Overall Survival prognosis of ChRCC (19). Our study results showed that age and T stages are essential in predicting survival prognosis for patients suffering from ChRCC. This is in similarity to the conclusion of the multi-institution study carried out by Ohashi, et al. (20).

More patients were found with AJCC stage I, which explained that despite the debates about the fact that ChRCC might also have the worst prognosis, ChRCC has a good Overall Survival rate and less metastasis spreading. TMN system is also known for its vital role in the choosing of the appropriate treatment before and after the surgery³. In that logic, Casuscelli, et al. (8) had conducted a study proving that T stage is an independent prognostic factor of OS for patients with ChRCC after nephrectomy. In addition had been proven in our study that patients diagnosed with T2, T3, M1 and even N1 did not have a favorable Overall Survival prognosis.

Second, sarcomatoid features and regional positive lymph nodes were found to be associated with ChRCC in our study. Sarcomatoid features and regional positive lymph-node were seen in less than 2% of our patients. his research supports previous findings that CHRCC has a better cancer-specific survival prognosis. However, those presenting these pathological features were closer to death than surviving. Also, in the past, the presence of sarcomatoid features and positive lymph-nodes had been associated with poor prognosis and therefore has not been known as favorable for Overall Survival(1).

Thirdly, even if there is still a debate on the effectiveness of chemotherapy, radiation therapy or oral inhibitors against ChRCC, they should be considered for the therapeutic treatment of ChRCC with T2, T3, M1 and N1 stages. Because of SEER terms and conditions, which recommend that radiation treatment data has many incomplete assessments, as does chemotherapy data with many caveats, we did not consider including the number of patients who received oncological therapy in our study. However, some studies have proved that patients on advanced stage or with pathological features could receive oral inhibitors, radiation treatment or chemotherapy after surgery(16).

Additionally, very few percentages of patients had their cause of death from the renal and pelvis. Even though this seemed positive information in our research of the Overall Survival prognosis of ChRCC, we still could not base on this

to make a conclusion because it had been proven in previous studies that ChRCC metastasis sites were most frequently spotted on the lung and liver (21).

To justify what was said above, we made a univariate regression analysis of the different pathological features to have the overall survival prognosis estimation ratio in ChRCC (Table 3).

Using vital status recode (study cutoff used) as the event variable, setting Alive as the positive event, and exploring the impact of other variables on the Vital status recode (study cutoff used). The value is greater than 1, and the previous is better. Less than 1, the latter comparison is better.

Example: The odds ratio between the grade groups I and II is 1.199. Odds ratios indicate that grade I are better at life status than patients with grade II.

The SEER database was mainly based on clinical results and lacked laboratory information. We hope that in future, there will be more laboratory studies about the ChRCC to ease the collection of information.

Conclusion

Chromophobe Renal Cell Carcinoma presents a favorable Overall Survival (OS) prognosis. Our study shows that significantly fewer patients present sarcomatoid features, which justifies the fact that ChRCC has a better Cancer-Specific Survival rate. However, those presenting sarcomatoid features with/without positive lymph-node have a poor prognosis. Although total nephrectomy remains the gold choice of treatment, we encourage that more future research should be done to develop a better oncological therapeutic treatment for those with metastasis.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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